

PREFERRED SCHOOL CULTURE AT SENIOR HIGH SCHOOLS DIVISION OF ZAMBALES: EXPLORING A SCHOOL CULTURE MODEL IN THE NEW NORMAL

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Abstract

This research was focused on the preferred school culture at Senior High Schools in the Department of Education (DepEd) Division of Zambales, Philippines which was conducted during the school year 2023. The respondents of this study were the Secondary School Heads and their respective Senior High School Teachers from the thirteen Districts of DepEd Schools Division of Zambales. The research design was descriptive; quantitative in its analysis (descriptive and inferential statistics); and utilized survey questionnaire as instrument for data gathering. Findings of the study revealed that the school heads are male, middle aged adults, Principal II, Master's degree holders with Doctorate units, and served in the profession for two and a half decades. The Senior High School teachers are female, young adults, Teacher II, Baccalaureate degree holders with Master's units; served in the teaching profession for less than a decade. The school heads highly preferred clan school culture while the teachers highly preferred hierarchy school culture for Senior High Schools. The study established a no significant difference in the perception on the preferred school culture at Senior High Schools when grouped according to the profile of the two groups of respondents. The present study created/designed a Senior High School Culture Model aimed to sustain the preferred culture of the senior high school organization.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, School Culture, School Heads, Senior High Schools, New Normal.

INTRODUCTION

In June 2020, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) published in June 2020 a paper intitled Education in a post-COVID world: Ideas for Public Action. The paper highlighted the idea that 'We cannot return to the world as it was before' and invites us to think about ways, principles, and possibilities to have no educational setback. This insight are also part of the discussion that involves school culture, and impulses us to think on the complexity, inter-relations and continuity of education, society and curriculum. Therefore, to guarantee continuity and to try to understand what this 'new normal' will demand of educators, it is essential to acknowledge how school culture and education relate to society.

The social and economic changes of the globalized world demand greater competences, which imply that school culture must adapt themselves to this demanding and challenging system (Gartner, 2020). Since according to Kızıloğlu (2021), the nature of organization's culture is the set of ideas and assumptions about organization's operation and interaction of employees with each other and with the management. Effective school management should include management of a productive organizational culture (Cameron & Quinn, 2005 and 2006).

Organizational culture is believed to be one of the determining factors for the success of the organization's performance. In the realization to the aims of the Senior High School to equip

learners with skills that will better prepare them for the future whether it be in employment, entrepreneurship, skills development, and higher education (Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013), according to Fitria (2018); and Kumar (2020) it is crucial to consider the role of leaders in the 21st century and in the ‘new normal’ set up in education system is urgently needed to provide proper support and coordination for workers; and enriching the main or dominant culture in the institution. A school principal is one of the most important components in school culture in improving the quality of education as for Dizon, et al. (2021), a principal holds direct responsibility for the management of education.

Schein (2004 cited in de Guzman, 2019) contend that many of the problems confronting leaders can be traced to their inability to analyze and evaluate organizational cultures and conditions of people. Many leaders, when trying to implement new strategies or a strategic plan leading to a new plans and reforms in the system will discover that their strategies will fail if they are inconsistent with the organization's culture. This study was premised on Quinn & Cameron (2005 cited in Chennatuserry, 2022) Competing Values Culture Framework. The researcher aspires to contribute to a broader knowledge in the variables presented. There is scarcity of research in the Senior High School levels in the Division of Zambales that explores school culture conditions preferred for the new normal educational landscape.

The empirical findings of the present study will also provide the educational administrators (school heads, principals and department heads) and teachers with critical insight on their preferred organizational culture and must be sustained aimed to contribute to a more empowered senior high schools in the ‘new normal’ education system. Moreover, this study would provide them the necessary and clear ideas in enhancing their skills as school managers and leaders of Senior High Schools. Moreover, study findings will further encourage Senior High teachers to further maximize their performance and capabilities as professionals and curriculum implementers in their most preferred school culture in this new normal. All of which contributes to attaining empowered teachers and schools. The lens of positive school culture to shape learning experiences with an eye toward helping the students, which inevitably determines the direction and effectiveness of education.

Statement of the Problem

This study investigated and determined the preferred school culture at Senior High Schools in the Division of Zambales, ways of ascertaining how basic educational institution during the post pandemic establish empowered schools. Specifically, the study answered the following specific questions:

1. How may the profile of the Senior High School Head and Senior High Teacher respondents be described as to gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, position/designation?
2. How may the Senior High School Head and Senior High Teacher-respondents describe their preferred school culture at public Senior High Schools in terms of: Clan, Adhocracy, Hierarchy, and Market?

3. Is there a significant difference in the perception on the preferred school culture at Senior High Schools when grouped according to school head-respondents' profile?
4. Is there a significant difference in the perception on the preferred school culture at Senior High Schools when grouped according to teacher respondents' profile?
5. What School Culture Model can be created aimed to sustain preferred features of school culture at Senior High Schools in the Division of Zambales?

MATERIALS & METHODS

In this research study, the researcher used descriptive design of research concerned mainly with describing events as they are without manipulation of what is being observed. The analysis of data is quantitative. According to Casadevall & Fang (2018), the descriptive method of research is a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, beliefs, processes, trends, and cause effect relationships. Descriptive research aims to describe a population, situation, or phenomenon accurately (Siedlecki, 2020). The present study investigated and described the preferred school at Senior High Schools in the Division of Zambales. It aims to ascertain how basic educational institution establish empowered schools this Division during the post pandemic.

This study has a total respondents of 255 (225 teachers and 30 principals/school heads). They are all employed in 32 Public Secondary Schools, Senior High School Department of DepEd, Division of Zambales, Philippines. The sample size for teachers was determined using the Slovin's formula. The study locale are the 13 Districts of DepEd Division of Zambales from Sta. Cruz District Candelaria District, Masinloc District, Palauig District, Iba District, Botolan District, Cabangan District, San Felipe District, San Narciso District, San Antonio District, San Marcelino District, Castillejos District, and Subic District.

The researcher utilized a survey questionnaire in gathering the data vital to the study. Deliquina & de Guzman (2021) considers the use of questionnaires in descriptive and social sciences research. Part I. This part obtained personal information about the respondents on areas such as gender, age, highest educational attainment, designation, length of service and position/academic rank. Part II of the questionnaire included items/indicators that assessed preferred school culture. The variables of school culture are clan, adhocracy, hierarchy, and market in Quinn & Cameron (2006) Competing Values Culture Framework (also discussed in Heinz, 2022); Chennatuserry, et al. (2022); and Pavlidou & Efstathiades (2021). Each of the cultural forms will have 10 indicators each. The answers of the respondents are within a 4-point scale ranging from (4) highly Preferred, (3) Preferred, (3) Not Preferred, and (1) highly Not Preferred.

The instrument in its first draft was presented to the experts on the field of school management and cultural anthropology of PRMSU Graduate School for validity purpose. Their ideas, suggestions and corrections were sought in terms of the extent of clarity, consistency, and suitability. The corrections/revisions were carried on in finalizing the research instrument. The conduct of a pilot test is necessary for the research instrument's test of reliability. The pilot test

was conducted among the principals and teachers at Senior High School Department of PCB, Botolan, Zambales. Cronbach's alpha was computed to test the reliability of the responses in the pilot test. Cronbach's Alpha values for School Culture are as follows: clan (0.953), adhocracy (0.920), hierarchy (0.927), and market (0.966).

The researchers sought the permission/approval of the DepEd Schools Division Superintendent, Division of Zambales to administer the survey questionnaire to the respondents. After securing the endorsement, the researcher personally distributed and retrieved the instrument to the respondents which was scheduled in February, 2023. The researcher explained the purpose/objective, relevance and significance of the study. Moreover, the researcher assured the respondents of the anonymity and confidential of their responses. The accomplished instruments were collected completely on third week of February 2023. Altogether 255 teachers and school heads filled out the instrument. For data analysis, the researcher used Frequency Count, Percentage and Weighted Mean, and Analysis of Variance. All the data gathered were tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted based on the statement of the problem.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Profile of the Senior High School Head and Senior High Teacher-Respondents of DepEd Division of Zambales

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Senior High School Heads and Teachers' Profile

Personal Profile Variables	School Heads		Senior High Teachers	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Gender				
Female	10	33.33	141	62.67
Male	17	56.67	80	35.55
LGBTQ+	3	10.00	4	1.78
Total	30	100.00	225	100.00
Age				
60-65 years old	4	13.33	3	1.33
50-59 years old	16	53.33	11	4.89
40-49 years old	7	23.33	49	21.78
30-39 years old	1	3.33	90	40.00
20-29 years old	2	6.67	72	32.00
Total	30	100.00	225	100.00
	Mean = 52.43 years old		Mean = 34.71 years old	
Highest Educational Attainment				
Doctors Degree	8	26.67	11	4.88
Master's w/EdD or PhD Units	10	33.33	20	8.89
Master's Degree	4	13.33	55	24.44
Bachelor w/ Master's Unit	7	23.33	102	45.33
Bachelor's Degree	1	3.33	37	16.44
Total	30	100.00	225	100.00
Length of Service				
36 years and above	3	10.00	1	0.44

31-35 years	3	10.00	1	0.44	
26-30 years	13	43.33	4	1.78	
21-25 years	6	20.00	6	2.67	
16-20 years	3	10.00	6	2.67	
11-15 years	2	6.67	11	4.89	
6-10 years	0	0.00	81	36.00	
0-5 years	0	0.00	115	51.11	
Total	30	100.00	225	100.00	
		Mean = 26.50 years	Mean = 6.70 years		
Designation	Frequency	Percent	Position	Frequency	Percent
Principal IV	5	16.67	Master Teacher III	4	1.78
Principal III	4	13.33	Master Teacher II	7	2.67
Principal II	11	36.67	Master Teacher I	7	2.67
Principal I	4	13.33	Teacher III	63	27.56
Head Teacher	7	20.00	Teacher II	92	40.89
Total	30	100.00	Teacher I	56	24.44
			Total	225	100.00

Gender. Of the 30 school head respondents, there are 17 or 56.67% male, 10 or 33.33% female and 3 (10.00%) are LGBTQ+. The result showed that more than half of the school administrators is represented by men. The result is consistent to the figures obtained by Cariño & de Guzman (2023) and Torres (2022). In their studies, secondary schools were headed by male administrators. However, women in the teaching profession appears to be rising steadily. Of the 225 respondents there are 141 (62.67%) female; 80 (35.33%) male; and 4 (1.78%) LGBTQ+. This means that more than half of the teachers employed in the senior high school are female. Women held about 76% of all teaching positions in public schools in 2017-2018 according to National Center for Education Statistics (UNESCO, 2020). On the other hand, majority of the respondents of the studies of de Guzman, et al. (2023); and Dizon Jr. (2021) are women.

Age. The mean age of the School Head teachers was 52.43 years old. This particular age is classified into middle aged adults. Middle aged adulthood is the period of development that occurs between the ages of 46-65 (Ericsson, Feltovich & Prietula, 2006, cited in de Guzman, et al., 2023), and as midlife adults with a strong sense of mastery and control over their lives. The mean age of the Senior High teachers was 34.71 years old. This particular age is categorized as young adults. According to Armstrong (2008) and Kessler, Brown & Broman (1981 as cited in Coching & de Guzman, 2023) young adults age ranges from 35 or 39 years old who often accommodate bigger, crucial and more complex responsibilities in life.

Highest Educational Attainment. Most of the school head respondents (10 or 33.33%) are holders of Masters with doctorate units. The findings that were obtained by Cariño & de Guzman (2023) on the demographic profile of public school heads found that majority or 75% of public school principals in Division of Zambales are holders of master's degree with EdD/PhD units. Obtaining an advanced studies opens doors for career growth and appointment to administrative or managerial position. Most (102 or 45.33%) of the Senior High School teacher-respondents are Bachelor degree holders with Master's units. This particular result is

consistent with result on the highest educational attainment profile variable of the studies of Coching & de Guzman (2023), and Deliquiña & de Guzman (2021) indicating that most of the teachers are holders of Bachelor Degree with Master's Units. Last October 26, 2021, the DepEd launched the Professional Development Program in line with its commitment to improve the quality of basic education in the Philippines.

Length of Service. The mean for the length of service of the school principal respondents is 26.50 years. The principals have rendered service in the teaching profession for more than two and a half decades. De Guzman (2019) deduced that school leaders' length of practicing their profession would further allow to develop the right preparation and expertise for leadership. The mean for the length of service of the teacher respondents is 6.70 years. The senior high school teachers have already rendered service in the teaching profession for more than half a decade. The DepEd Senior High School Qualification Standards, 2016 stipulates that one (1) year relevant teaching/industry work-experience is the experience requirement for SHS Qualification Standards.

Position/Designation. Most of the school heads are Principal II (11 or 36.67%), followed by Head Teachers and Principals IV respectively. This particular result is coherent with the results of the studies of Cariño & de Guzman (2023) and de Guzman, et al. (2023). The majority of the school head respondents of their studies are Principal II. Principals are expected to spearhead in setting the direction and strategy of the school through efficiently and transparently managing the fiscal and asset resources of the school (DepEd Memo 19, s 2016). Almost half of the respondents (92 or 40.89%) are Teacher II; followed by Teacher III, and Teacher I respectively. In comparable to this result, Teacher II was also the academic position that constituted the largest percentage of the teacher-respondents in the studies of Lipawen & de Guzman (2022). In the DepEd Order No. 019 s.2022, the Department of Education Merit Selectin Plan ensures that the Department hires the right people for the right job by adhering to the principle of merit.

2. Perception of School Heads and Senior High Teachers on the Preferred School Culture at Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Zambales

The **School Heads'** highly preferred school culture at public senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales in terms of clan school culture was indicator 9, the school values and highly prioritizes teamwork and employee involvement (WM=3.87, rank 1). The school heads' highly preferred a school that values and prioritizes teamwork and employee involvement. Building a sense of team unity in the new normal setting is important for growth and moral support as the school year begins. The respondents preference shows manifestations of the school upholding provision and essence of Republic Act No. 9155 known as Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001. The Act aims to strengthen School-Based Management (SBM) of DepEd Order. No. 55, s. 2008 by further devolving the governance of education to schools, empowering school teams and personnel, expanding community participation and involvement, and making the delivery of education to the learners more responsive, efficient, and effective.

2.1. Clan. Table 2 presents the perception on the preferred school culture in terms of Clan.

Table 2: Extent of School Heads and Senior High Teachers' Preference on Clan as a School Culture

Clan	School Heads			Senior High Teachers		
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
1. The school focuses more on and interested in their internal outcomes	3.70	Highly Preferred	9	3.31	Highly Preferred	8.5
2. The employees and staff of this school trust their managers and colleagues	3.80	Highly Preferred	5.5	3.36	Highly Preferred	4.5
3. The school's employees do things together; the manager build teams and rewards teams	3.83	Highly Preferred	3	3.44	Highly Preferred	1
4. The school manager focuses attention on the people who make up the team	3.73	Highly Preferred	7.5	3.31	Highly Preferred	8.5
5. The school capitalizes on coaching and mentoring	3.73	Highly Preferred	7.5	3.32	Highly Preferred	7
6. The school manager focuses its attention on employee's wellbeing, health and personal goals	3.83	Highly Preferred	3	3.36	Highly Preferred	4.5
7. The school promotes flexibility in terms of dress code, hours and working locations	3.57	Highly Preferred	10	3.30	Highly Preferred	10
8. The school adopts family-like culture; more 'inclusive' approach; and welcoming ideas and feedback with open arms	3.80	Highly Preferred	5.5	3.36	Highly Preferred	4.5
9. The school values and highly prioritizes teamwork and employee involvement	3.87	Highly Preferred	1	3.36	Highly Preferred	4.5
10. The school as organization promotes teamwork, participation, and consensus	3.84	Highly Preferred	2	3.40	Highly Preferred	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.77	Highly Preferred		3.35	Highly Preferred	

The respondents in the study of Chennatuserry, et al. (2022) prefer a culture that provides for the development of human capital, promotes high trust and employee engagement, and offers an opportunity to participate in decision-making. These are manifestations of clan culture. Discussed in the studies of Steve Gruenert (2020) and de Guzman (2019) that in a team, teachers have ample learning opportunities and professional participations that will help them grow both personally and as a group.

Indicator 7, the school promotes flexibility in terms of dress code, hours and working locations obtained the least weighted mean of 3.57 (rank 10). This result was also the response of the teachers in senior high school Division of Zambales (Table 2, WM=3.30 rank 10) Still, the school heads highly value and promote flexibility in terms of dress code, hours and flexibility of work. In the new normal setting as a visual expression, identity and policy implementation, schools' dress code carries immense significance for all members of the organization. Research concludes (de Guzman, 2019; and Cameron & Quinn, 2006) that while there is no standard dress code, there is a system where each industry identifies trends to promote optimum efficiency.

On the other hand, school leaders that allow their staff the freedom to work a flexible schedule can also find themselves a more desirable organization that people want to work for most especially in time of health crisis and post pandemic. In the Philippines flexible working hours shall apply only to all non-teaching personnel in the Central, Regional, and Schools Division Offices (DepEd Order No. 23, S. 2018). Overall, the school heads/principals' perception of clan school culture at senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales was 3.77 (OWM) with qualitative rating of Highly Preferred.

The **Teachers'** highly preferred school culture at public senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales in terms of clan school culture was indicator 3, the school's employees do things together; the manager build teams and rewards teams (WM=3.44, rank 1). They highly preferred to work at a school in which school heads focused on building efficient and effective teams and appreciating them of their efforts and expertise.

Clan culture is promoted if schools practices recognizing deserving and performing school employees. According to De La Cruz (2019), the school manager direct individual accomplishments toward organizational objectives. Moreover, pursuant to DepEd Order 9, s. 2002 as reinforced by DepEd Order 78, s. 2007 entitled Strengthening the Program on Awards and Incentives for Service Excellence (PRAISE) shall serve as reference in ensuring that the most outstanding personnel is duly recognized and awarded.

Indicator 7 stating that the school promotes flexibility in terms of dress code, hours and working locations obtained the least weighted mean of 3.30 and was least from the rank (rank 10). This result was also the response of the school heads in senior high school Division of Zambales (see Table 2).

The teachers also highly preferred a clan culture primarily when school promotes flexibility in terms of dress code, hours and working locations. This signifies that having a more relaxed dress code provides them more comfort, more freedom to express their individuality; and preferred that their school heads allow work flexible schedules.

Cameron, Quinn, et al. (2006 cited in de Guzman, 2019) argued that in clan culture of an organization, employee welfare through flexible schedules is one of the most important incentives/privilege employees want from their employers. Overall, the teachers perception of clan school culture at senior high schools of Division of Zambales was 3.35 (OWM) with qualitative rating of Highly Preferred.

2.2. Adhocracy

Table 3 presents the perception on the preferred school culture at Senior High Schools in terms of Adhocracy.

Table 3: Extent of School Heads and Senior High Teachers' Preference on Adhocracy as a School Culture

Adhocracy	School Heads			Senior High Teachers		
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
1. The school can foster competition between employees as the pressure to come up with new ideas	3.50	Highly Preferred	10	3.13	Preferred	10
2. Employees of this school have a strong commitment in creating new standards	3.53	Highly Preferred	9	3.35	Highly Preferred	4
3. The school maintain continuous improvement and innovation	3.57	Highly Preferred	7.5	3.44	Highly Preferred	1
4. The school constantly find creative solutions and looking to develop the next big thing	3.57	Highly Preferred	7.5	3.36	Highly Preferred	3
5. The school do new things, create, innovate, envision the future	3.67	Highly Preferred	6	3.40	Highly Preferred	2
6. The school can easily handle discontinuity, change, and risk	3.73	Highly Preferred	3.5	3.30	Highly Preferred	6
7. The school's employees enjoy freedom of thoughts and action	3.77	Highly Preferred	2	3.28	Highly Preferred	9
8. The school's employees conduct thoughtful experimentation, and learning from mistakes	3.80	Highly Preferred	1	3.34	Highly Preferred	5
9. The school's employees are visionaries inclined toward risk, not afraid of uncertainty	3.73	Highly Preferred	3.5	3.29	Highly Preferred	7.5
10. In this school, the power is not centralized, it flows from individual to individual or team to team	3.70	Highly Preferred	5	3.29	Highly Preferred	7.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.66	Highly Preferred		3.32	Highly Preferred	

The **School Heads'** highly preferred school culture at public senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales in terms of adhocracy school culture was indicator 8, the school's employees conduct thoughtful experimentation, and learning from mistakes (WM=3.80, rank

1). The school heads highly preferred to manage a schools in the new normal where employees conduct thoughtful learning from mistakes most especially in professional context (for instance in instruction, assessment and reporting of students' performance; and aptitude and other decisions and actions). The respondents in the study of de Guzman (2019) highly manifest the belief that teachers are not infallible, teachers make mistakes. In adhocracy culture set-up, Cameron, et al. (2006); and Fu, et al. (2022) posits that there should really be just as much emphasis placed on helping teachers to develop a growth mindset themselves

Indicator 1, the school can foster competition between employees as the pressure to come up with new ideas mounts obtained the least weighted mean of 3.50 (rank 10). This was also the least preferred of the teacher respondents of the present study (Table 3, WM=3.13, rank 10). A senior high school that can foster competition between employees with the foremost reason to improve and to grow as educational institution was highly preferred feature of adhocracy culture from the perspective of the school head respondents.

Healthy competition in the new normal education should manifest in instruction and other professional endeavors. Fitriana, et al. (2022) stressed that adhocracy organizational culture suggests that by working together, team members can push one another to be more productive and produce stronger work. Overall, the school heads' perception on adhocracy school culture at senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales was 3.66 (OWM) with qualitative rating of Highly Preferred.

Highly preferred school culture at public senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales in terms of adhocracy school cultures was indicator 3, the school maintain continuous improvement and innovation (WM=3.44, rank 1) form the insights of the **teachers**. The school that maintains continuous improvement, development and innovation are what the senior high school teachers preferred in the new normal setting in education.

According to de Guzman (2019) and Dinko (2022) claimed that schools most particularly in the 21st century and in the new normal of education have to focus on innovations and manage to harness technology to raise productivity, improve efficiency, increase quality and foster.

Indicator 1, the school can foster competition between employees as the pressure to come up with new ideas obtained the least WM of 3.13 (rank 10). This was also the response of the school heads/principals (see Table 3). The teachers also preferred to be a member of a school in the new normal that reflects features of adhocracy culture mainly fostering competition between employees aims to further improve and grow for the better.

Competition between employees is an inevitable part of most people's work before the worldwide crisis, post pandemic and new normal. Competition can motivate employees, make them put in more effort and achieve results (Cameron, et al., 2006) and contributes to higher performance (Cameron & Quinn, 2006 as discussed in Fitriana, et al., 2022). Overall, the teachers' perception of adhocracy school culture at senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales was 3.32 (OWM) with qualitative rating of Highly Preferred.

2.3. Hierarchy. Table 4 presents the perception on the preferred school culture at Senior High Schools in terms of Hierarchy.

Table 4: Extent of School Heads and Senior High Teachers' Preference on Hierarchy as a School Culture

Hierarchy	School Heads			Senior High Teachers		
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
1. The school have a set way of doing things, have clear direction which makes them stable	3.67	Highly Preferred	3.5	3.32	Highly Preferred	10
2. The school focuses on structure and stability. It aims for getting done right	3.67	Highly Preferred	3.5	3.40	Highly Preferred	1.5
3. The school managers are reliable, organized and well-informed experts	3.63	Highly Preferred	5.5	3.40	Highly Preferred	1.5
4. The employees of this school focus on attention to details, precise analysis and careful decisions	3.63	Highly Preferred	5.5	3.39	Highly Preferred	3
5. The school is characterized as conservative, cautious, logical problem solvers	3.60	Highly Preferred	8	3.34	Highly Preferred	8.5
6. The school brings structure, rigor and control to operations and operating processes.	3.60	Highly Preferred	8	3.37	Highly Preferred	6
7. The school's policies ensure order, efficiency and consistency and with strict protocols.	3.60	Highly Preferred	8	3.35	Highly Preferred	7
8. The school's practices lie in the stability, process control and predictability that it gains.	3.57	Highly Preferred	10	3.34	Highly Preferred	8.5
9. The school ensures that things are done in smooth, ordered and controlled ways.	3.73	Highly Preferred	1	3.38	Highly Preferred	4.5
10. The school's work environment is considered well defined and formal	3.70	Highly Preferred	2	3.38	Highly Preferred	4.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.64	Highly Preferred		3.37	Highly Preferred	

The **school heads'** highly preferred school culture at public senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales in terms of hierarchy school culture was indicator 9, the school ensures that things are done in smooth, ordered and controlled ways (WM=3.73, rank 1). They highly

preferred schools that ensures work, tasks and plans that are done on point, orderly and controlled. This situations can be achieved by a particular school if rules, regulations, policies and guidelines are well considered and upheld. For instance, The DepEd issued guidelines on the Organizational Structures and Staffing patterns of Public Senior High Schools; National Qualifying for School Heads; Guidelines for the Implementation of CSC Resolution; Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) to name some.

Schools and other education settings are complex learning communities, involving many different roles and functions. In order for schools to be safe, and maintain supportive environments, there is a need to have a clear procedures, structures, and expectations in place (Omenyi & Emengini, 2020). In the new normal setting, school leaders need to look at the function of school policies (Dinko, 2022).

Indicator 8, the school's practices lie in the stability, process control and predictability that it gains obtained the least weighted mean of 3.57 (rank 10). Even least from the rank, this feature of hierarchy culture was still highly preferred. The school heads highly approved stability and practiced process control. Ensuring school stability as characteristics of hierarchy culture promotes positive learning experiences, engagement in school, and steady learning. For Chennatuserry, et al. (2022), institution characterized by hierarchy culture focuses in providing students with stable support which builds up a feeling of acceptance that lasts. Overall, the school heads' perception of hierarchy school culture at senior high schools was 3.64 (OWM) interpreted as Highly Preferred.

The **teachers'** highly preferred school culture at public senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales in terms of hierarchy school culture was indicator 2, the school focuses on structure and stability. It aims for getting done right; and indicator 3, the school managers are reliable, organized and well-informed experts (WM=3.40, rank 1.5 respectively). Highly preferred characteristics or dimensions of hierarchy school culture in the present study was determined by senior high teachers on aspect of stability of school structure in the new normal education; also on aspect of getting works done the right way; and considering themselves as well-informed experts. De Guzman (2019); and Shah, et al. (2021) claimed that schools with a strong and reliable school management were highly preferred and supported by their respondents.

Although indicator 1, stating that the school have a set way of doing things, have clear direction which makes them stable obtained the least weighted mean of 3.32 and least from the rank (rank 10), still this is highly preferred by the senior high school teachers of Division of Zambales. Preferred high school culture manifestations are the shared orientations, values, norms (vision and mission), and practices that hold their unit/department together. Chennatuserry, et al. (2022) stressed that managers who sustain hierarchy culture have a key role to play in setting direction, proactive school mindset, and commitment needed to foster improvement and promote success for schools in challenging circumstances. Overall, the perception on hierarchy school culture at senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales was 3.37 (OWM) which means Highly Preferred.

2.4. Market. Table 5 presents the perception on the preferred school culture at senior high schools in terms of Market Culture.

Table 5: Extent of School Heads and Senior High Teachers' Preference on Market as a School Culture

Market	School Heads			Senior High Teachers		
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
1. The school as organization are often competitive and work to win	3.73	Highly Preferred	3	3.39	Highly Preferred	3.5
2. The school employees are often competitive, and leaders set high expectations.	3.74	Highly Preferred	2	3.35	Highly Preferred	6
3. The school is highly client focused and prioritize doing a great job for clients.	3.80	Highly Preferred	1	3.44	Highly Preferred	1
4. The school's core values are based on winning and biting all rivals	3.43	Highly Preferred	9	3.17	Preferred	10
5. The school's top performers are rewarded and highly recognized, encouraging them to go the extra mile for their employers.	3.70	Highly Preferred	5.5	3.34	Highly Preferred	7
6. The school prioritizes customer satisfaction, shareholder value, and competitors,	3.70	Highly Preferred	5.5	3.42	Highly Preferred	2
7. The school focuses on speed, getting things done, and achieving goals	3.63	Highly Preferred	7	3.38	Highly Preferred	5
8. Deliver results, make fast decisions, solve problems	3.71	Highly Preferred	3	3.39	Highly Preferred	3.5
9. Leaders are hard-driving, directive, commanding, demanding	3.	Highly Preferred	8	3.28	Highly Preferred	8
10. In this school, there is a high chance of work stress or employee burnout.	3.25	Preferred	10	3.19	Preferred	9
Overall Weighted Mean	3.63	Highly Preferred		3.34	Highly Preferred	

The **school heads** highly preferred school culture at public senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales in terms of market school culture was indicator 3, the school is highly client focused and prioritize doing a great job for clients (WM=3.80, rank 1). This result is consistent with the perception of the teachers on preference on market as a school culture (Table

5, WM=3.44 rank 1). The school heads' prefer to work in a school in which the employees highly focused on their respective tasks; on their clients; and prioritizes superior job and output for clients' satisfaction. This could also mean that the school heads highly prefer to utilize and implement monitoring (e.g., observation of classes, evaluation of teachers' performances to name some) tools used to ensure quality instruction, management and clients satisfaction. Moreover, the senior high schools of the present study are client focused, a clear characteristic of market culture.

Effective leader in a market culture is oriented toward service of customers' needs and greatest possible satisfaction, developing partnerships beyond the school to encourage parental support for learning and new learning opportunities (Heinz, 2022; and de Guzman, 2021); leaders are not running a one-man show (Pavlidou & Efstathiades, 2021).

Indicator 10, in this school, there is a high chance of work stress or employee burnout obtained the least weighted mean of 3.25 (rank 10) and preferred feature of market school culture from the perspective of the school heads/principals. They preferred a senior high school with lesser chance of work stress or employee burnout. This particular result indicates that employees of their respective school have already experienced high risk stress-related concerns during the pandemic and in the new normal. Overall, the perception of school heads on market school culture at senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales was 3.63 (OWM) with qualitative rating of Highly Preferred.

The **teachers'** highly preferred school culture at public senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales in terms of market school cultures was indicator 3, the school is highly client focused and prioritizes doing a great job for clients (WM=3.44, rank 1). The teachers highly favored a school setup which centers on clients service and produces output/outcomes. This result is consistent with the preference of the school heads on market school culture (see Table 5). Their leaders knew well how they can optimize the interaction between clients (parents, students, and teachers). Moreover, school heads prioritize senior high students acquisition of quality education in the new normal; and personal and professional development of educator implementers.

Now more than ever, school leadership, parents and educators need to prioritize student well-being, in all aspects along with academic learning (Deal & Peterson, 1998 as cited in Kumar, 2020). Market school identity in which the school leadership keeps on figuring out how they are going to prioritize their commitments was preferred (Torres, 2022); and everything towards increasing productivity and efficiency) (Heinz, 2022).

Indicator 4, the school's core values are based on winning and biting all rivals obtained the least weighted mean of 3.17 (rank 10). This indicator was least from the aspects of market culture. For the teachers, they still preferred that their school's core values are based on winning and competitiveness. Senior high schools also compete in different events such as academic and sports and they are serious in training their students to compete on these. According to Cameron & Quinn (2006); Heinz (2022); and de Guzman (2019), organization must be clear that developing the right attitudes and attributes in people such as resilience, respect,

competitiveness, and creativity that fosters positive culture. Overall, the teachers' perception of market school culture at senior high schools of Division of Zambales was 3.34 (OWM) with interpretation of Highly Preferred.

Table 6: Summary on the Extent of the School Heads and Senior High School Teachers' School Culture Preference

Preferred School Culture at Public Senior High Schools	School Heads			Senior High School Teachers		
	Overall Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank	Overall Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
Clan	3.77	Highly Preferred	1	3.35	Highly Preferred	2
Adhocracy	3.66	Highly Preferred	2	3.32	Highly Preferred	4
Hierarchy	3.64	Highly Preferred	3	3.37	Highly Preferred	1
Market	3.63	Highly Preferred	4	3.34	Highly Preferred	3
Grand Mean	3.68	Highly Preferred		3.35	Highly Preferred	

Clan obtained OWM=3.77 (rank 1st) interpreted as Highly Preferred. The Grand Mean was 3.68. The school heads highly preferred Clan School Culture at senior high schools in the Division of Zambales. On the Other hand Hierarchy was Highly Preferred by the Senior High reached with OWM=3.37 (rank 1st). The Grand Mean was 3.35. Overall, the school heads in the Division of Zambales highly preferred the features and characteristics of Clan Culture, while the teachers' highly preferred Hierarchy School Culture.

3. Analysis of Variance on the Difference in the Perception on the Preferred School Culture at Public Senior High Schools when grouped according to School Head Respondents' Profile

Table 7: Summary in the Difference in the Extent of Preference on School Culture when grouped according to School Heads' Profile

Sources of Variations	Clan Culture		Adhocracy Culture		Hierarchy Culture		Market Culture	
	Mean Square	Sig.	Mean Square	Sig.	Mean Square	Sig.	Mean Square	Sig.
Age	0.04	0.74	0.14	0.43	0.06	0.70	0.26	0.20
Gender	0.00	0.91	0.02	0.75	0.06	0.48	0.09	0.47
Highest Educational Attainment	0.11	0.29	0.10	0.57	0.27	0.08	0.07	0.77
Length of Service	0.05	0.74	0.05	0.88	0.06	0.84	0.19	0.35
Position/Designation	0.12	0.13	0.25	0.09	0.21	0.10	0.06	0.83

*Significant

Clan. The significance values for age (0.74), sex (0.91), highest educational attainment (0.29), length of service (0.74), and position/designation (0.13) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance. Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis. There is no significant difference in the extent of preference on Clan as a school culture when grouped according to the school heads'

profile. Whether the respondents vary in their personal profile, their knowledge, practices, and beliefs towards preferred aspects of Clan culture are alike. A clan culture is people-focused on the sense that the company feels family-like (Cameron & Quinn, 2005 as cited in Heinz, 2022).

Adhocracy. The significance values for age (0.43), gender (0.75), highest educational attainment (0.57), length of service (0.88), and position/designation (0.09) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance.

Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis. There is no significant difference in the extent of preference on Adhocracy as a school culture even the respondents' profile varies. The perceptions of the respondents of the studies of Dinko (2022); and Torres (2022) bare no difference even they are new or quite long as serving as head of their Department, differ in educational qualifications and trainings as administrators or managers.

Hierarchy. The significance values for age (0.70), gender (0.48), highest educational attainment (0.08), length of service (0.84), and position/designation (0.10) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance.

Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis. There is no significant difference in the extent of preference of the school heads on Hierarchy as a school culture even they vary in terms of their personal profile. The result on the perceptions of the school administrators in the study of Omenyi & Emengini (2020), signifies no difference most particularly the emphasis on building shared core values, top-down decision-making, and internal predictability is known as a hierarchical culture.

Market. The significance values for age (0.20), gender (0.47), highest educational attainment (0.77), length of service (0.35), and position/designation (0.83) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance. Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis.

There is no significant difference in the extent of preference of the school heads on Market as a school culture when attributed to their personal profile. The school heads in the study of Pavlidou & Efstathiades (2021) showed similar perception, knowledge and preference to the elements of market culture such as priority to outcome and product and competition. Output, gains and results drive work initiatives to motivate employees.

4. Analysis of Variance on the Difference in the Perception on the Preferred School Culture at Public Senior High Schools when grouped according to Teacher Respondents' Profile

Clan. The significance values for age (0.61), gender (0.29), highest educational attainment (0.51), length of service (0.15), and position/designation (0.95) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance. Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis.

There is no significant difference in the extent of preference on Clan as a school culture in senior high schools in the Division of Zambales. Results could be merited on the similarity of the orientation knowledge and practiced manifestations of the aspects of Clan culture in their respective school even though they differ in their personal attribute/profile.

Table 8: Summary in the Difference in the Extent of Preference on School Culture when grouped according to Senior High Teachers' Profile

Sources of Variations	Clan Culture		Adhocracy Culture		Hierarchy Culture		Market Culture	
	Mean Square	Sig.	Mean Square	Sig.	Mean Square	Sig.	Mean Square	Sig.
Age	0.17	0.61	0.08	0.85	0.11	0.77	0.15	0.62
Gender	0.28	0.29	0.27	0.29	0.52	0.15	0.09	0.53
Highest Educational Attainment	0.21	0.51	0.34	0.23	0.44	0.13	0.39	0.13
Length of Service	0.39	0.15	0.31	0.26	0.52	0.06	0.43	0.06
Position/Designation	0.05	0.95	0.16	0.64	0.22	0.48	0.23	0.39

***Significant**

Adhocracy. The significance values for age (0.85), gender (0.29), highest educational attainment (0.23), length of service (0.26), and position/designation (0.64) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance.

Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis. There is no significant difference in the extent of preference on Adhocracy as a school culture in the Division of Zambales when grouped according to the teachers' profile. Culture can also help to attract top talent, as employees want the opportunity to think outside the box at work.

Hierarchy. The significance values for age (0.77), gender (0.15), highest educational attainment (0.13), length of service (0.06), and position/designation (0.48) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance. Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis.

The senior high school teachers signify the likeness of perception on the manifestations of hierarchy as a school culture even the teachers differ in their personal profile. Considering the identified difference in personal profile of the respondents of the study of Omenyi & Emengini (2020), their perceptions are alike. Creating a structure that aligns with the organization's goals is essential.

Market. The significance values for age (0.62), gender (0.53), highest educational attainment (0.13), length of service (0.06), and position/designation (0.39) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance. Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis.

There is no significant difference in the perception on the preferred aspects of the Market as a school culture even though they differ in their personal profile. Heinz (2022) revealed that results are what matter most in market culture. In this environment, leaders need to be both hard workers and competitors because they must be demanding and have high expectations for the staff.

5. School Culture Model Designed Aimed to Sustain Preferred Features of School Culture at Senior High School in the Division of Zambales

The School Culture in this study is thought and assumed to be the preferred and acquired body of knowledge, beliefs, values, norms, artifacts, actions/rituals and patterns shared and whose interpretation and understanding provide the identity of the school as an organization and a sense of shared identity among its members. The school culture can paved the way to sustain an empowered senior high schools in DepEd Division of Zambales in the new normal. The preferred clan culture is towards establishing and sustaining desirable work relationship and conditions; reliable school management (hierarchy); learning and skills development (adhocracy); and positive school culture for excellence (market).

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that:

1. The Senior High School Heads are male, middle aged adults, Master's degree holders with doctorate units, Principal II, and have served in the profession for two and a half decades while the Senior High School Teachers are female, young adults, baccalaureate degree holders with master's units, Teacher II and have served as professional teachers for less than a decade.
2. The school heads highly preferred clan school culture for senior high schools largely the practice of valuing and prioritizing teamwork and employee involvement while the teachers highly preferred hierarchy school culture for senior high schools predominantly on the school employees' practice of doing tasks/duties together; and having a school head that build teams and rewards teams.

3. There is no significant difference in the perception on the preferred school culture at public senior high schools when grouped according to school head respondents' profile.
4. There is no significant difference in the perception on the preferred school culture at public senior high schools when grouped according to teacher respondents' profile.
5. A Senior High School Culture Model was designed aimed to sustain the preferred features of school culture in the DepEd Division of Zambales.

RECOMMENDATIONS

With the above presented conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were advanced:

1. The School Heads of Senior High Schools in the Division of Zambales may conduct more activities for school employees prioritizing the building of teamwork and employee involvement.
2. The School Heads may prioritize and implement regular school-based merit and reward system for individual and group's exemplary outputs and achievements
3. The School Heads may conduct regular and close monitoring of enforcement of school policies, rules and regulations for orderly, organized and stable school management.
4. The School Heads may devise a scheme in which teachers in this department will practice more involvement in planning and decision making of school projects and programs
5. Present the Senior High School Culture Model to the School Heads, Supervisors and Education Specialist of DepEd Division of Zambales for review and critiquing, and consideration for policy implementation.
6. Conduct a follow up study outside the Division of Zambales (Public and Private Senior Secondary Schools) to validate the findings of the present study.

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